

Research on the Performance and Application of a Low-Carbon Waste-Recycling Cement

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Abstract:

This paper mainly introduces the history of the formation and development of an ultra-high performance low-carbon waste-utilizing cement (fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement). This cement not only uses a large amount of solid waste (fly ash, blast furnace slag, industrial waste gypsum, alkali slag, etc.) as raw materials, and the waste utilization can reach 40%~95%, but also has a calcination temperature of 150~200°C and 50 °C lower than that of traditional ordinary Portland cement and sulphoaluminate cement, and the carbon emission is equivalent to 30%~60% and 50%~80%. Through the elaboration of its main

mineral composition, chemical composition, physical properties and action mechanism, the reasons for its excellent properties such as good whiteness, fast setting and hardening, high late strength, and small dimensional deformation are analyzed. And the application research is focused on the fields of inorganic flooring, airports, road quick repair, prefabricated walls, ultra-light and efficient A-level fire insulation, cement crafts, inorganic artificial stone, and UHPC ultra-high performance concrete. At present, there are many types of low-carbon cement in the world, including Porsol cement, Alinit cement, Celitement cement, Japanese eco-cement, multi-component high-mixture cement, high-belite cement, Anther cement, BCT cement, etc., but most of the products have a slow coagulation and hardening speed, and cannot meet the needs of rapid demolding, turnover, and traffic opening for mortar, concrete, cement products or pavements; at the same time, the production process is complicated and cumbersome, the later strength is low, the deformation is large, and the durability is poor. Therefore, in the actual promotion process in the engineering field, there are great difficulties and many constraints. Among them, Aether cement and BCT cement belong to the belite-sulfoaluminate cement system. Aether cement has 6h early strength performance. Compared with Portland cement (burning temperature

1400~1500°C), it can significantly reduce production energy consumption, reduce CO₂ emissions by 25%~30% per ton of cement, and the 28-day compressive strength reaches the strength level of standard cement (CEM I 52.5R); the size shrinkage of this concrete is less than 50% of that of OPC concrete, but its raw materials still use limestone, bauxite, gypsum, iron raw materials and marl raw materials, without effective utilization of bulk industrial waste, and CO₂ emissions are far from meeting the low-carbon environmental protection requirements. BCT cement can be produced at a lower temperature (1250~1300°C), and its raw materials use industrial waste residues such as limestone, marl, fly ash and industrial by-product gypsum. CO₂ emissions are 30% lower than traditional OPC cement clinker, but there is no early hourly strength, and the strength after 1~2 days is higher than that of ordinary Portland cement. This is far from the goal of using bulk industrial waste as raw materials to produce green, low-carbon, energy-saving and high-performance cement materials, which is currently widely used at home and abroad. At the same time, the above-mentioned low-carbon cement cannot effectively and reasonably control key indicators such as cement whiteness value, early strength before 4 hours, and dimensional change rate, and cannot meet the requirements of high-performance cement. At the same time, the production process is not mature and stable enough, and there is still a long way to go to meet the comprehensive popularization of production industrialization and promotion scale.

Keywords: *Waste-Recycling Cement Materials, Recycled Materials in Construction, Low-Carbon Waste Materials, Recycled Construction materials.*

Introduction

The research presented in this paper explores the development, performance, and potential applications of an innovative low-carbon, waste-recycling cement known as fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement. This novel cement was developed by Tangshan Polar Bear Building Materials Co., Ltd. in 2014 and has since gained recognition through multiple patents in China, the United States, and South Korea. This research aims to contribute to the ongoing efforts to mitigate environmental impact and promote sustainability in the construction industry by leveraging industrial waste materials and reducing carbon emissions.

Background and Rationale

The production of traditional Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) is known to be energy-intensive and a significant contributor to global CO₂ emissions. As the construction industry continues to grow, there is a pressing need for alternative materials that can reduce the environmental footprint. The development of high-belite sulphoaluminate cement represents a promising solution to this challenge. Unlike conventional cement, this innovative cement

utilizes a significant proportion of industrial waste materials such as fly ash, blast furnace slag, and industrial by-product gypsum, which can replace natural raw materials. This not only helps in reducing the dependency on natural resources but also aids in managing industrial waste effectively.

Composition and Properties

High-belite sulphoaluminate cement is characterized by its unique chemical composition, which includes low iron oxide content, and its incorporation of a variety of active and inactive mixed materials. The primary constituents include fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement clinker, gypsum or industrial by-product gypsum, and slag. The resulting cement boasts several advantageous properties, including high whiteness, low alkalinity, rapid setting and hardening, high early and late strength, minimal dimensional deformation, and excellent resistance to cracking, corrosion, and carbonization. Furthermore, the production process of this cement involves a lower calcination temperature compared to OPC, resulting in reduced energy consumption and lower emissions of pollutants.

Environmental and Economic Benefits

The environmental benefits of this cement are substantial. The lower calcination temperature, approximately $1300\pm 50^{\circ}\text{C}$, compared to $1450\text{--}1500^{\circ}\text{C}$ for OPC, results in significant energy savings. Additionally, the use of industrial waste materials can replace up to 95% of traditional raw materials, thereby reducing the environmental impact of cement production. The lower CO_2 emissions associated with this process are estimated to be 30-60% less than those of OPC, aligning with global efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and combat climate change.

From an economic perspective, the utilization of industrial waste materials not only reduces the cost of raw materials but also addresses the issue of waste disposal. This can result in significant cost savings for the construction industry while promoting sustainable practices. The high early strength of this cement also facilitates rapid construction processes, reducing project timelines and associated costs.

Applications

The versatility of high-belite sulphotoaluminate cement makes it suitable for a wide range of applications. It has been successfully used in inorganic flooring, airport and road repairs, prefabricated walls, fireproofing and thermal insulation, cement handicrafts, inorganic artificial stone, and ultra-high performance concrete (UHPC). Each application leverages the cement's fast-setting and hardening properties, high strength, and resistance to environmental factors.

For instance, in the field of road and airport repairs, the rapid setting and high early strength of the cement allow for quick reopening of traffic, minimizing disruptions. In the construction of prefabricated walls, the cement's high strength and durability ensure long-lasting structures. Its use in fireproofing and thermal insulation applications is particularly noteworthy, as it offers both lightweight and high-efficiency solutions.

Comparative Analysis

When compared to other low-carbon cements available globally, such as Porsol cement, Alinit cement, Celitement, Japanese eco-cement, and various multi-component high-mixture cements, high-belite sulphotoaluminate cement stands out for its rapid setting and hardening properties. Many alternative cements, while effective in reducing CO_2 emissions, often suffer from slow setting times, lower early strength, and greater dimensional deformation, limiting their applicability in time-sensitive construction projects.

Challenges and Future Research

Despite its advantages, the adoption of high-belite sulphotoaluminate cement is not without challenges. The production process, while less energy-intensive than that of OPC, still requires optimization to enhance stability and scalability. Further research is needed to refine the production techniques and expand the range of waste materials that can be utilized. Additionally, long-term performance studies are necessary to fully understand the durability and environmental impact of this cement over extended periods.

Fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphotoaluminate cement is a high-performance low-carbon cement developed by Tangshan Polar Bear Building Materials Co., Ltd. in 2014. It has obtained 2 Chinese invention patents, 1 American invention patent, and 1 Korean invention patent. The cement is a (white) hydraulic cementitious material with crack resistance, fast setting and fast hardening properties made by grinding (low iron oxide content) fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphotoaluminate cement clinker, appropriate amount of gypsum or industrial by-product gypsum, slag and other active or inactive mixed materials. The cement has high whiteness, low alkalinity, fast coagulation and hardening, high early strength, high late strength, small dimensional deformation, no cracking, good corrosion resistance, good carbonization resistance, low total heat release, fine surface, high gloss and other excellent properties. At the same time, during the production and

calcination process, the cement has a low firing temperature, uses industrial waste as raw materials, and has low pollution emissions. It is a high-performance, low-cost, low-carbon cement. As a new type of low-carbon solid waste cement, it has the following three advantages:

- (1) Energy saving: The calcination temperature of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulpho-aluminate cement clinker is $(1300\pm 50)^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is $150\sim 200^{\circ}\text{C}$ lower than that of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) clinker and 50°C lower than that of ordinary sulpho-aluminate cement (CSA) clinker.
- (2) Utilization of waste: The raw materials of clinker are all derived from industrial waste (fly ash or blast furnace slag is used to replace bauxite, industrial waste gypsum is used to replace natural gypsum, and alkali slag is used to replace high-quality limestone). 40%~95% of industrial waste can be added.
- (3) Low carbon: The carbon emissions of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite

sulphoaluminate cement are only 30% to 60% of P·O42.5 and 50% to 80% of CSA42.5 cement. The global annual cement production forecast data is shown in Figure 1 (data source, World Wildlife Fund WWF), and the carbon dioxide emissions of OPC (ordinary Portland cement clinker), CSA (sulphoaluminate cement clinker), and HB-CSA (fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement clinker) are shown in Figure 2.

The mineral compositions of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulpho-aluminate cement clinker, fast-hardening sulpho-aluminate cement clinker and ordinary Portland cement clinker are shown in Table 1. The comparison values of the free expansion rates of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulpho-aluminate cement (42.5 grade crack-resistant double fast) and the 42.5 grade ordinary silicate cement produced by Qinhuangdao Asano Cement Plant in North China and the 42.5 grade ordinary silicate cement produced by Tangshan Jinyu Jidong Company are shown in Table 2.

Figure 1. Annual Cement Production Forecast

Figure 2. Carbon Emissions from Cement Clinker

Table 1. Mineral Composition of Different Cement Clinkers (%)

Clinker Varieties	C_3S	C_2S	C_3A	C_4AF	C_4A_3S	F-CaO	$CaSO_4$
HB-CSA	0	35~45	0	1~3	20~35	0.5~4.5	15~25
CSA	0	15~30	0	3~25	50~70	0	A small amount
OPC	44~62	18~30	5~18	10~18	0	≤1.0	0

Table 2. Comparison of Cement Free Expansion Rates

Cement Varieties	28 day free expansion 1%		90 day free expansion 1%	
	Dry Air	Water	Dry Air	Water
Polar Bear Company level (42.5 Anti-cracking double-quick cement)	0.004	0.06	-0.008	0.046
Qinhuangdao Asano Company (42.5 Grade Silicon Cement)	-0.15	0.039	-0.17	0.050
Tangshan Jinyu Jidong Company (42.5 Grade Silicon Cement)	-0.21	0.038	-0.21	0.038

Chemical Composition and Physical Properties

According to the different whiteness values of cement, it can be divided into two series: white anti-crack, fast-setting and fast-hardening high belite sulphoaluminate cement (abbreviated as:

white anti-crack double-fast cement) and anti-crack, fast-setting and fast-hardening high belite sulphoaluminate cement (abbreviated as: anti-crack double-fast cement). The chemical composition is shown in Table 3, the physical properties are shown in Table 4, and the strength index is shown in Table 5.

Table 3. Chemical Composition of Cement (%)

Cement	LOI	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	TiO ₂
White Crack resistant Double Quick cement	0.46	17.53	14.82	1.16	46.65	4.86	12.96	0.63
Anti-Cracking Double-Quick Cement	0.55	18.39	14.64	0.96	46.02	5.41	12.57	0.63

Table 4. Physical Properties of Cement

Project	Specific Surface area m ² /kg	Setting Time/Min		28 Day free Expansion Rate 1%		Whiteness value
		Intial Setting	Final Setting	Water	Ten Voids	
White Anti-cracking double fast cement	≥450	≥15	≤45	≤0.08	≥-0.05	70
Anti-cracking double fast cement	≥450	≥15	45	≤0.08	≥-0.05	

Table 5. Strength Index of Cement

Project	Compressive Strength, MPa			Flexural Strength, MPa		
	4 hours	7 days	28 days	4 hour	7 days	28 days
White crack resistant double quick cement	≥12.5	≥32.5	≥42.5	≥4.0	≥5.0	≥6.0

Hydration Mechanism

Fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement contains 35%~45% C₂S (dicalcium silicate), 20%~35% C₄A₃S (anhydrous calcium sulphoaluminate), 1%~3% C₄AF (calcium aluminoferrate), 0.5%~4.5% f-CaO (free calcium oxide), and 15%~25% f-CaSO₄ (free gypsum). Its mineral composition is essentially different from that of traditional silicate cement and sulphoaluminate cement. The phase composition of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement at the hydration age is the following hydration reactions:

- (1) $C_4A_3S + 2CS + 38H \rightarrow C_3A \cdot 3CS \cdot 32H$ (high sulfur type calcium sulfonate) + 2AH₃ (aluminum gel)
- (2) $C_3A \cdot 3CS \cdot 32H \rightarrow C_3A \cdot CS \cdot 12H$ (low-sulfur calcium sulfonate) + 2CSH₂ (dihydrate gypsum) + 16H
- (3) $C_2S + H_2O \rightarrow CSH$ (hydrated calcium silicate gel) + CH

In the early stage of cement hydration, C₄A₃S in cement reacts quickly with CaSO₄ to form calcium sulfonate and aluminum gel (basically consumed within 4 hours of hydration), so it has the performance of rapid coagulation and rapid hardening, and the early strength develops rapidly. As the hydration continues, coarse needle-shaped calcium sulfonate and tubular calcium sulfonate are generated, and the hydration products gradually increase; among them, the needle-shaped calcium sulfonate is staggered and overlapped to form a skeleton, and the gel phase such as aluminum gel is filled in the skeleton, which plays the role of filling and bonding, making the structure of the hardened cement paste more compact, so the strength of the cement paste gradually increases. Therefore, it has the excellent performance of small shrinkage deformation, high late strength and good durability.

White crack-resistant, fast-setting and fast-hardening high belite sulphoaluminate cement is made by strictly controlling the content of C₄AF in the crack-resistant, fast-setting and fast-hardening high belite sulphoaluminate cement,

and using the relative proportion of f-CaO and f-CaSO₄ in the components, achieving a breakthrough in the whiteness index of fast-setting and fast-hardening high belite sulphoaluminate cement, with a whiteness value of over 70. Therefore, this series of cement has the advantages of good whiteness, good whiteness stability, fast hardening speed, low dimensional deformation and high later strength, and is very suitable for the preparation of cement-based products, panels or fluid mortar surface layers with high decorative effects.

Application of Fast Setting and Hardening High Belite Sulphoaluminate Cement

Due to the high early strength of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement (4h strength > 12.5 MPa), it can realize rapid demoulding and turnover of cement-based products and is widely used in the field of

prefabricated walls; because it can significantly improve the early strength and late strength of ordinary cement after compounding with ordinary cement, it is used to make ultra-light and high-efficiency Class A fireproof insulation panels; due to its good whiteness and high fineness (whiteness value > 70), it can be used to make decorative, delicate and bright cement-based handicrafts; due to its small dimensional deformation and dimensional change rate < 0.08%, it can be used in the field of inorganic self-leveling and inorganic terrazzo flooring; due to its high early strength, it can have ultra-early functions within 1 h after adding some admixtures, and the deformation is further reduced, so it can be used in the field of quick repair of airports and roads; due to its continuous increase in late strength, it takes into account the performance of early demoulding and late high strength, and is used in the field of inorganic artificial stone, UHPC ultra-high performance concrete bridges and exterior wall panels.

Figure 3. Application of Inorganic Flooring

Application of Inorganic Flooring

The fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement, colored aggregates,

functional additives, and water are added to make a fluid colored terrazzo mortar, which is then hardened and polished. It can be made into various inorganic floors with diverse styles and

shapes according to the overall needs of the architectural design. Compared with traditional tile floors, concrete floors, marble floors, terrazzo floors, epoxy floors, etc., this floor has many advantages such as good fluidity, fast construction speed, low shrinkage, good crack resistance, wide range of leveling thickness, one-time leveling, various architectural styles, and can be designed according to needs. It is widely used in different areas such as shopping mall lobbies, hotel lobbies, airport lobbies, brand flagship stores, and highway service areas. The application of this technology in the field of inorganic flooring is shown in Figure 3.

Application in airport and road rapid repair fields

Key parts such as airport pavements and highway pavements are subjected to heavy loads for a long time, and are subject to heavy wear, which can easily cause surface damage or local defects. The use of traditional ordinary cement mortar, sulphoaluminate cement mortar, composite cement mortar, magnesium cement mortar, polymer mortar, etc. has large shrinkage, poor bonding strength, and poor water resistance. After repair, it will cause falling off and hollowing in a short time, which cannot meet the actual application needs. The use of

organic products such as epoxy resin mortar and polyurethane mortar has high bonding strength, but there are serious problems with durability in long-term outdoor applications, and the price is very expensive.

The airport pavement mortar made of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement, graded aggregate, high molecular polymer and functional additives can meet the needs of repairing different thicknesses of 5~200 mm. The compressive strength of the mortar can reach more than 50 MPa 1 hour after the construction is completed, the flexural strength can reach more than 10 MPa (concrete flexural strength is more than 5 MPa), the bonding strength with the base layer can reach more than 2 MPa in 1.5 hours, and the dimensional change rate is within 0.03%. It meets the needs of airports and highway pavements to quickly restore traffic load. At present, this product is used in the strategic reserves of major military airports and civil airports, the emergency repair and construction of highways, and the rapid maintenance of key roads. The application of this technology in airport runways, aprons and roads is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Application in Airport and Road Rapid Repair Fields

Application in the Field of Prefabricated Walls

With the development of the national economy, steel structure assembly has been widely promoted and applied. Its structural form is mainly large-span frame, with high construction standards and good functional requirements. In order to meet the requirements of the frame light panel system, large-sized lightweight and high-strength steel structure assembly composite wall panels are widely favored by the construction market. However, the traditional cementitious materials are made of ordinary silicate cement, fly ash, fine sand, etc., mixed with water, and then made into polymer mortar for smearing and pressing to make the surface layer of composite wall panels. The operation is difficult, the crack resistance is poor, the coagulation and hardening time is long, and the production efficiency is low. It is very unfavorable for the industrialization, automation, and large-scale production of steel structure assembly composite wall panels, which

seriously affects the development speed and comprehensive promotion of the building structure assembly industry.

The process uses a six-sided coating of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement, graded aggregates, and functional additives as the surface layer, and the middle is filled with Class A fireproof insulation core materials (such as rock wool, cement foam insulation, thermosetting insulation materials, etc.). It has good crack resistance, fast coagulation and hardening, high early and late strength, and is made into a composite wall panel integrating structure and insulation using a flat mold production process. This product is widely used in frame buildings such as industry, residential buildings, hotels, office buildings, shopping malls, schools, hospitals, etc. The application of this technology in the exterior walls of the Yanshan University Gymnasium and the Handan No.1 Middle School Gymnasium is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Application of Prefabricated Wall

Application of Ultra-Light and High-Efficiency Class A Fireproofing and Thermal Insulation

At present, China's building energy consumption accounts for about 30% of the total social energy consumption. If no energy-saving and emission-reduction measures are taken, more than 50% of my country's energy consumption will be spent on buildings; the walls of my country's residential buildings account for about 40% of the energy loss, and the external insulation technology of building exterior walls has become the dominant direction of my country's building energy-saving technology. For a long time, organic insulation materials have the advantages of low density and good thermal insulation effects, and have dominated the market, but they have the serious defect of not being fireproof. Although inorganic insulation materials have good fireproof properties, they have high density and high thermal conductivity, which are far from meeting the energy-saving index requirements. When the density is low, the tensile strength is low, and the safety of the external wall insulation structure system cannot be guaranteed.

The composite cement formed by ordinary silicate cement and high belite sulphoaluminate cement, combined with modified basalt fiber, is formed by chemical foaming to form an ultra-light composite cement foam insulation board with a dry density of $\leq 120 \text{ kg/m}^3$, thermal conductivity of $\leq 0.048 \text{ W/(m}\cdot\text{K)}$, compressive strength of $\geq 0.25 \text{ MPa}$, and tensile strength of $\geq 0.1 \text{ MPa}$. From the perspective of material performance, it solves the shortcomings of traditional cement foam insulation boards, such as high density, poor insulation effect, and low compressive strength. At the same time, the high tensile strength and excellent fire resistance give the exterior wall insulation material not only good durability, but also completely eliminate fire hazards.

After high-strength double-fast high-belite sulphoaluminate cement and ordinary Portland cement are compounded in a certain ratio (30%:70%), the hydration reaction rate of ordinary

Portland cement is greatly accelerated, so that the demoulding time of the cement-based foam insulation board formed after the compounding is greatly shortened, the early strength is significantly improved, and the later strength continues to increase, which completely solves the problem of easy cracking of ordinary Portland cement foam insulation board. At the same time, adding less than 60% of solid waste fly ash into the cementitious material solves the practical problems of fly ash occupying a large amount of land, wasting land resources, polluting soil, affecting plant growth and the production of breeding and animal husbandry, turning harm into benefit, turning waste into treasure, and realizing the comprehensive utilization of fly ash. The application of this technology in exterior wall insulation is shown in Figure 6.

Application of Cement Handicrafts

Semi-hydrated gypsum, magnesium oxide, and special cement products harden quickly and are widely used in indoor handicrafts, pendants, tables and chairs, countertops, fireplaces, etc., as well as outdoor rockeries, sculptures, logos, flower pots, etc. However, gypsum products are air-hardening materials with poor water resistance and wear resistance. Magnesium oxide products are prone to brine and deformation when exposed to moisture. Traditional special cement products shrink greatly and carbonize severely in the later stage. The above products have many defects in the field of inorganic handicrafts, which is also an important factor restricting the development of the field of inorganic handicrafts.

The color slurry made by mixing fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement, selected aggregates, functional additives, and pigments with water in a certain proportion has the remarkable advantages of fine surface, good waterproof performance, strong carbonization resistance, minimal shrinkage, fast early demoulding, high strength in the later stage, and good durability. Therefore, it is widely used in the market for indoor and outdoor decorative components, GRC components, and GRC

crafts. The various applications of this technology in the field of inorganic crafts are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Application of Class A Fire Proofing and Thermal Insulation

Figure 7 Application of Cement Handicrafts

Application of Inorganic Artificial Stone

With the dual policy orientation of transformation and upgrading of the stone industry and environmental protection rectification, as well as the central environmental protection supervision to the local "two cuts and three clears", the environmental protection requirements of the stone industry are constantly upgraded. If enterprises want to seek green and sustainable development, they must enhance their ability of scientific and technological innovation, develop advanced material technology, production and processing technology and advanced manufacturing equipment, realize automation, intelligence, and large-scale production, improve production efficiency, reduce energy consumption, and reduce environmental pollution. White crack-resistant high-belite sulphoaluminate cement,

decorative aggregates such as graded quartz sand (tempered glass, shells, colored sandstone, jade, agate, metal, etc. can be used to form a variety of colors) are used as the base material, and high alkali-resistant fiber, pigment, and functional additives are added as raw materials. Through the process of mixing and conveying → pouring and paving → setting thickness and leveling → grinding and polishing, inorganic artificial stone panels with excellent decorative effects are made. The inorganic artificial stone panels made by this technology have the advantages of fast coagulation and hardening, small dimensional deformation, and high mechanical strength, which solves the common problems of low strength, low production efficiency, alkali return, large shrinkage, and easy deformation and cracking of inorganic artificial stones made of traditional white silicate cement as the main body.

Figure 8. Application of Inorganic Artificial Stone

The inorganic artificial stone slabs made of white crack-resistant high-belite sulphoaluminate cement, slag powder, composite retarder and other functional additives as raw materials, combined with solid waste iron tailings, copper tailings, granite tailings, gold tailings and other aggregates through mixing → spreading → pressing → curing → grinding and polishing and deep processing can reduce the water absorption rate of the slabs to below 0.1% and the glossiness to above 90. Its comprehensive performance can meet the various standard requirements of quartz stone in T/CSBZ 009-2019 "Technical Specifications for Inorganic Artificial Stone (Pressing Plate Method)", which can not only replace the application of natural stone and organic resin stone, but also avoid the environmental problem of a large amount of pollution generated during the mining of natural stone, and solve the problem that the resin stone is not wear-resistant enough for the ground and has poor weather resistance for the exterior wall. The application of this technology in the field of inorganic artificial stone is shown in Figure 8.

Application of UHPC Ultra-High Performance Concrete

In recent years, the demand for concrete in the field of building materials has increased

significantly in terms of both dosage and technical level. With the development of the concept of green building, decorative concrete with decorative functions has become a hot topic in recent years; at the same time, technological progress in the field of concrete has also led to the development of ultra-high performance decorative concrete (UHPC). However, ultra-high performance concrete based on traditional white cement and silicate cement has the defects of slow hardening speed, large shrinkage deformation, and low flexural strength. The UHPC ultra-high performance concrete, which is mixed with fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulfoaluminate cement, fine aggregate, functional additives, fiber and water, has a 4-hour compressive strength of more than 60 MPa, a 28-day compressive strength of 150 MPa, a flexural strength of more than 30 MPa, and a 28-day shrinkage rate of less than -0.04%. Different flow properties can be formulated to meet the application needs of ultra-high performance concrete products such as curtain walls and decorative concrete and different construction processes. The application of this technology in UHPC exterior wall scrapers and prefabricated components is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Application of UHPC Ultra-High Performance Concrete

Conclusion

The raw materials for clinker of low-carbon waste-utilizing cement (fast-setting, fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement) are all derived from industrial waste (fly ash or blast furnace slag is used instead of bauxite, industrial waste gypsum is used instead of natural gypsum, and alkali slag is used instead of high-quality limestone). Cement can be blended with 40% to 95% of industrial waste, which solves the problem of natural waste materials occupying arable land, polluting the air, and having adverse effects on people and the environment.

The calcination temperature of this series of cement clinker is (1300 ± 50) °C, which is 150~200°C lower than that of ordinary Portland cement (OPC) clinker and 50°C lower than that of ordinary sulphoaluminate cement (CSA) clinker. The carbon emission of fast-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement is only 30%~60% of that of P·O42.5 cement and 50%~80% of that of CSA42.5 cement.

Rapid-setting and fast-hardening high-belite sulphoaluminate cement contains 35%~45% C_2S (dicalcium silicate), 20%~35% C_4A_3S (anhydrous calcium sulphoaluminate), 1%~3% C_4AF (calcium aluminoferrate), 0.5%~4.5% f-CaO (free calcium oxide), and 15%~25% f- $CaSO_4$ (free gypsum). Its mineral composition is essentially different from that of traditional silicate cement and sulphoaluminate cement.

The 4h strength of this series of cement is greater than 12.5 MPa, which can achieve rapid demoulding and turnover of cement mortar or concrete products. The dimensional deformation of the free expansion rate in the dry state is equivalent to 1/50 of that of ordinary silicate cement at 28 days and 1/20 of that of ordinary silicate cement at 90 days. It has good crack resistance. By controlling the whiteness of raw materials and admixtures, cement with a whiteness value of more than 70 can be industrially produced.

This series of cement has been widely promoted and applied in the fields of inorganic flooring, airports, quick road repairs, prefabricated walls, ultra-light and high-efficiency A-level fireproofing and thermal insulation, cement handicrafts, inorganic artificial stone, UHPC ultra-high performance concrete, etc.

Author Contributions

Md Monir Hossain: investigation, funding acquisition, and writing – original draft preparation, Syed Mohammed Walid Karim: writing original draft preparation, data analysis, writing – review and editing, and checking the original draft; Toki Thamid Zim: writing – review and editing and checking the original draft; Md Mahmudul Hasan: investigation, funding, acquisition; Md Tanvir Ejaj Tushar: checking the original draft, and writing – review and editing; Anik Md Shahjahan: checking the original draft and data analysis. All authors have accepted responsibility for the entire content of this manuscript and approved its submission.

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